

FLEAS INFESTING DOGS, CATS AND GOATS IN DISTRICT NOWSHERA AND MARDAN KHYBER PAKHTUNKHWA PAKISTAN

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Abstract

Introduction: Fleas are blood-sucking ectoparasites of humans and domesticated animals like dogs, cats, and goats. More than 2,500 species of fleas have been identified worldwide. Fleas are the vectors of many pathogens like Rickettsia felis which causes flea-borne spotted fever, Rickettsia typhi which causes murine typhus and Bartonella species which are the causative agents of Bartonellosis. Fleas can cause disease in animals as well as in humans. In Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan information about the flea fauna infesting cats, dogs, and goats were limited. Here in, we conducted comprehensive morphological analysis for the identification of fleas infesting dogs, cats, and goats in districts Nowshera and Mardan.

Materials and methods: About 338 flea specimens were collected from December to June from different areas including Mardan (Takhtbhai, Rashaka, and Sheikh Maltoon) and Nowshera and from different hosts like dogs, cats, goats and were preserved in 70% ethanol. For identification; fleas were washed with distilled water and morphologically identified by using morphological keys under stereomicroscope.

Results: In collected fleas, Ctenocephalides felis were 287 (84.9%) which were collected from dogs (251 fleas), cats (26 fleas), and goats (10 fleas), Ctenocephalides canis 4 (1.1%) collected from dogs, and 47 (13.9%) specimens of Pulex irritans were collected from dogs (45 fleas), and cats (2 fleas).

Conclusion: Ctenocephalides felis shows high infestation rate then Ctenocephalides canis and Pulex irritans in our study. This was the first study of flea morphology infesting dogs, cats and goats in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Pakistan and we further evaluate about best morphological pictures of other fleas and also for their pathogen like Rickettsia species. Our study will contribute to the understanding of flea morphology and their pathogenicity in animals and humans.

INTRODUCTION

Fleas (Insecta, Siphonaptera) are tiny insects that are flattened from side to side, lack wings, and are highly adapted to their environment. They play a significant role as carriers of disease-causing agents across various regions globally. Both adult male and female

fleas are mandatory blood-feeding external parasites that infest mammals and birds. Fleas can cause severe damage to these animals and effects their health and productivity also. Approximately 2,574 flea species, classified into 16 families and 238

genera, have been identified; however, only a small number of these species live in close association with humans (synanthropic) that is they live in close association with humans (Bitam et al., 2010). About 563 species or 34 % of the total number of species that have been recorded have been reported with monoxenous status from a single host species. Although about one-sixth of these species are confirmed to be monoxenous (restricted to a single host species), most are still only known from a few specimens collected from just one host species.

On this point fleas are leading all other ectoparasitic groups as they have the majority of species in the order of fleas that can parasitize more than one number of host species (Medvedev, 2017).

Fleas have historically been epidemiologically important not only due to their bites but also because they serve as arthropods vector for various pathogenic bacteria that cause infectious diseases and can cause severe damage to animals and humans (Zurita et al., 2024).

The evolution of fleas occurs in the early Cretaceous or Jurassic ages between 125 to 150 million years ago together with the evolution of marsupials (pouched mammals) and insectivores (insect-eating mammals). Fleas serve various roles as parasites in mammals: they can transmit pathogens as vectors, act as intermediate hosts for immature parasites, and cause discomfort as ectoparasites, sometimes triggering allergic reactions in animals and humans. (Dobler and Pfeffer, 2011).

It is important to emphasize the impact of climate change on the epidemiology and distribution of vectors arthropods, including fleas. Temperature affects not only the vector but also the pathogens they transmit as their ability to multiply is influenced by temperature. This impacts not only the pathogens themselves but also their interactions with viruses, bacteria and parasites (Caminade et al., 2019). With a few exceptions, adults in this order are obligate blood-sucking ectoparasites of warm-blooded (that regulate their body temperature) vertebrates. Because fleas need a blood meal before they can lay eggs, their distribution depends on the presence of suitable hosts, although a few species with catholic tastes (that can affect various numbers of hosts) are cosmopolitan (worldwide distributed) in their distribution (Lewis, 1998).

The *Ctenocephalides felis* subspecies includes; the cosmopolitan or worldwide sub specie *Ctenocephalides felis felis* (Cadiergues et al., 2000), an Asian subspecies (lives in Asia) *Ctenocephalides felis orientis* (Shakya et al., 2018) and two subspecies that are restricted to the African continent: *Ctenocephalides felis strongyles* (Jordan, 1925) and *Ctenocephalides felis damarensis* (Jordan, 1936). Since their original description, *Ctenocephalides felis orientis* and *Ctenocephalides felis damarensis* have been morphologically reclassified as full species (*Ctenocephalides felis orientis* and *Ctenocephalides felis damarensis*, respectively), but the genetic identity of the *C. felis* subspecies remains elusive or difficult to find (De Meillon et al., 1961; Louw and Horak, 1995; Beaucournu and Menier, 1998; Menier and Beaucournu, 1998). It remains unknown whether worldwide *Ctenocephalides felis* populations are genetically homogenous and cannot be distinguished (Beaucournu and Menier, 1998; Lawrence et al., 2014, 2015a).

Currently, this insect has emerged or re-emerged around the world and may affect a wide range of animals. Owing to the climate change effects, vector-borne pathogen distribution and host ranges and their diseases can be changed and shows different symptoms in different animals (Bitam et al., 2010).

In the North of Iran, fleas from dogs were collected by (Azarm et al., 2016) in which *Ctenocephalides canis* were the most abundant flea present in dogs. About 20 dogs were examined and fleas were collected from them. 942 fleas were collected of which 98.73% fleas were *Ctenocephalides canis* and 1.27% was *Ctenocephalides felis*. *Ctenocephalides* were 100% infesting dogs in Meshkinshahr. (Shakya et al., 2018) find out the occurrence of *Ctenocephalides orientis* in goats and dogs in Madhya Pradesh. They collected fleas and preserved them in 70% ethanol and then they dehydrated them in 30%, 50%, 80%, and absolute ethanol and classified fleas as *Ctenocephalides orientes*. They separate these fleas from other fleas based on their morphological characteristics like tibia, genal comb, and abdominal segments bristles. (Lawrence et al., 2019) find out the human-mediated dispersal of *Ctenocephalides felis* or cat fleas and find out their subspecies and their morphological

identification in 2019. They collect fleas from 57 countries from dogs and cats.

Our main objective was to morphologically identify fleas infesting dogs, cats and goats for the first time in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Pakistan which will be very beneficial for medical sciences and for further researches.

2. Materials and methods

Total of about (338) fleas specimens were collected from dogs, cats, goats, and mice in KPK province; the climate of the province varies with elevation. The mountain ranges encounter cold winters and cool summers, whereas the temperature rises towards the south.

In Nowshera Cantonment, the temperature typically varies from 43°F to 111°F and annual rainfall is 131.34 mm. Mardan is located in the south west of the district at 34°12'0N 72°1'60E and an altitude of 283 meters (928 ft.) Mardan District of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Mardan features a hot and semi-arid climate. The average annual temperature is about 29°C. June is the warmest month of the year here, with an average temperature of 39°C. January is the coldest month in Mardan, and temperature is low in this month, with average temperature of 18°C (Hayat et al., 2024) **figure 1**.

We gathered fleas using a fine-toothed comb, focusing especially on the head, neck, sides of the

body, tail, and underside of each animal. We checked about 200+ animals in which we collected (338) fleas from (45) host animals. Over (50) pigeons were checked for fleas but we do not collect any fleas from the pigeons we collected the mites from them and also collect fleas from their dirt. We examine (94) dogs and collected (300) fleas from (33) dogs. We also checked (13) cats and (45) goats and we collected (28) fleas from (3) cats and (10) fleas from (4) goats. For the collection we used gloves, masks, and forceps, we also provide some food for the animal to make him feel comfortable. We place the fleas in eppendorf tubes and preserved it in 70% ethanol which is very best for preservation. We store the tubes at room temperature at the parasitology lab and we place tubes separately and note their data of host and also environmental conditions.

For morphological identification we first clean the specimen with distilled water. For the morphological analysis, all complete specimens were carefully examined and photographed under a stereo microscope for initial species identification. The morphology of fleas was studied by using different keys figures and descriptions used previously (Van der Mescht et al., 2021; Garcia Sanchez et al., 2022; Hopkins and Eothschil, 1953; Linardi and Santos, 2012; Lawrence et al., 2014).

Figure 1. Map showing districts of collection.

3. Results

Total of (338) flea specimens were collected and were arranged (287) as *C. felis* (74) males and (213) females, (4) as *C. canis* (2) males and (2) females and (47) as *P. irritans* (17) males and (30) females (**Figure 2 & 3**). **Table 1** shows the geographical area and the fleas collected from that area.

Geographical location	C. felis Number		C. canis Number		Pulex Irritans Number	
	Male	Female	Male	Female	Male	Female
Nowshera Kalan	2	2	-	-	2	4
Sheikh Maltoon	1	1	-	-	-	2
Missal Abad	5	24	1	1	-	-
Shoro Mandy	3	7	-	-	11	19
Dairy farm Nowshera	-	3	-	-	-	-
Khatkaly	-	4	-	-	-	-
Gul Abad	4	25	-	-	-	-
Mandro	7	11	-	-	-	2
Pampoo Kaly	2	5	-	-	1	1
Sapyako Kaly	-	6	-	-	1	1
Kati Garhy	34	67	-	1	2	-
Gadbano Kaly	3	4	-	-	-	-
Aslam Kaly	-	6	-	-	-	-
Nawa Kaly	2	18	-	-	-	1
Mandoory River area	3	11	-	-	-	-
Mirzada Kaly	8	19	1	-	-	-
Total	74	213	2	2	17	30

Table 1. Geographical areas and fleas collection.

Statistical Analysis

For statistical analysis Microsoft office suite, specifically word and excel were utilized for various purposes like pie diagram that shows different species Percentages, histogram for showing the exact

numbers of males and females of *Ctenocephalides felis*, *Ctenocephalides canis*, and *Pulex irritans* and charts showing different geographical areas and hosts with flea gender and species.

Figure 2. The percentage of *Ctenocephalides felis*, *Ctenocephalides canis* and *Pulex irritans*.

Figure 3. Graphical presentation of collected male and female species of different fleas.

Hosts	No	<i>C. canis</i>	<i>C. felis</i>	<i>P. irritans</i>
Dogs	300	4	251	45
Goats	10	-	10	-
Cats	28	-	26	2
Total	338	4	287	47

Table 2: Shows different hosts and fleas which are collected from them

Ctenocephalides felis

Ctenocephalides felis fleas have a genal comb as well as a pronotal comb. The head length is twice its width. The genal comb has more than 5 spines and is pointed horizontally. The first spine of the genal comb is already equal in size to the second spine in the genal comb, these fleas have 6 notches in their hind leg tibia and also have one short stout bristle in the interval between post median and long apical

bristle of the dorsal margin of the hind tibia which was shown in the **Figure 4**.

Male and female identification

Males are smaller in size than females also males are flatter than females. The head of the male is more rounded than female while the female head is not so rounded and is more football-shaped or has more slopes.

Figure 4. *Ctenocephalides felis* (A)Female (I) Genal comb 1st spine is already equal to 2nd one in size (II) Having pronotal comb (III) Having six notches on their hind tibia (IV) Single spine in hind tibia (V) Head is not strongly rounded and is slightly flat (B) **Male** (I) Having pronotal comb (II) Genal comb, size of 1st spine is already equal to the second one (III) Six notches (IV) Single spine in hind tibia (V) Head is not flat like in female and is slightly rounded (VI) Upper side of the body is flatter than female.

Figure 5. *Pulex Irritans* (A) Female (I) No genal comb (II) No pronotal comb (III) No contracted thorax and its expanded (IV) Single row of bristles on abdominal segments (B) Male (I) No genal comb (II) No pronotal comb (III) Rounded head (IV) No contracted thorax (V) Backward area is moves towards up.

***Ctenocephalides canis* (dog flea)**

These fleas have a pronotal and genal comb. Head of these fleas are blunt or more rounded in shape. 1st spine in the genal comb is half of the 2nd spine or remaining spines. There are 8 numbers of notches in the hind tibia of these fleas and they have 2 bristles in the hind tibia after the interval. Males of these fleas are smaller than females and are also flatter like *Ctenocephalides felis* and *Pulex irritans* (Figure 6).

Figure 6. *Ctenocephalides canis* (A)Male (I) 1st spine is half of the 2nd one (II) Having pronotal comb (III) Having strongly rounded head (IV) Having genal comb (V) Having two spines on the hind tibia and eight notches (VI) Back area is moved upward(B)Female(I)1st spine is half of the 2nd one in length (II)Having pronotal comb

(III) Head is not rounded and is flatter than male (IV) Having genal comb (V) Having two spines in the hind tibia and 8 notches are present (VI) Backside area is normal and is not moves upward.

Figure 7. *Ctenocephalides felis* female collected from dogs, cats and goats.

Figure 8. *Ctenocephalides felis* male collected from dogs and cats.

Figure 9. *Pulex irritans* male collected from dogs.

Figure 10. *Pulex irritans* females collected from dogs and cats.

Figure 11. Fleas collected from cats (I) *Ctenocephalides felis* male (II) *Pulex irritans* female. (III) *Ctenocephalides felis* female. (IV) *Ctenocephalides felis* female. (V) *Ctenocephalides felis* female.

Figure 12. Fleas collected from goats (I) *Ctenocephalides felis* female (II) *Pulex irritans* female (III) *Ctenocephalides felis* male

Discussion

In our present study, we further evaluate the morphological identification of fleas as given by (Azarm et al., 2016) which was only regarding *Ctenocephalides felis* and *Ctenocephalides canis* and was conducted in Iran. We provide complete detail on the morphological identification of Genus *Pulex* and *Ctenocephalides* for the first time in Pakistan.

Our results show that the most prevalent species in dogs is *Ctenocephalides felis* which is known as cat flea and its prevalence in dogs is about (84.9%) and about 251 specimens of *Ctenocephalides felis* were collected.

The lower numbers of *Ctenocephalides canis* also show that this specie is present at lower rates than *Ctenocephalides felis* (Dobler and Pfeffer, 2011) and we collected only 4 specimens of *Ctenocephalides canis*.

We collected the fleas in the winter season (December, January, and February) and also in hot season, and in hot season we collected more fleas than in winter season which shows that fleas have high infestation rate in hot seasons as compared to cold season.

Fleas were more abundant in dogs as compared to cats and goats. Fleas were more in the place where the temperature is high like in Kati Garhy (Mardan) have more temperature so here we collected 104 fleas (Table 1).

We also separated fleas collected from dogs, cats, and goats and add their pictures with complete descriptions and characters which were not present collectively in one single paper like in (Lawrence et al, 2014; Shakya et al,2018).

Ctenocephalides felis females collected from dogs, cats and goats were shown in one figure (Figure 7) and also males *Ctenocephalides felis* male were shown in (Figure 8) they show little variations in their morphology but we do not differentiate the subspecies *Ctenocephalides felis* like in (Lawrence et al, 2014) but we provide complete information on morphology on specie level.

Spermatheca is best for differentiation between males and females of *Ctenocephalides felis* male and female (Lawrence et al, 2014; Shakya et al, 2018) which is our limitation in this study. Mesopleuron is also important for differentiation between *Pulex irritans* and *Xenopsylla cheopis* but we do not differentiate on that character.

In (Gracia et al., 2008; Millan et al., 2007; He et al., 1997; Christodoulouopoulos et al., 2006) *Pulex irritans* male and female pictures were not separately given and therefore we separately make figures of males and females (Figure 9 and Figure 10). *Pulex irritans* which is known as human flea is more prevalent in dogs as compared to goats and cats.

The present study were actually conducted to find out the infestation rates of different fleas and to provide complete information about fleas morphology in district Nowshera and Mardan. Our results shown that *Ctenocephalides felis* had high infestation rate as compare to other fleas (*Ctenocephalides felis*>*Pulex irritans*>*Ctenocephalides canis*).

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